

Red! I am in Love, I am enraged! A note on the risk of eliciting negative emotions

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Abstract

What if Red had multiple meanings? And what if its various meanings were opposing and contradicting to one another? Furthermore, what would it be like if colors were all correlated with both positive and negative associations and/or emotions? If this were the case, would we work with color differently and with greater caution when attempting to create desired user-experiences? Would we look to mitigate the negative emotions and support the positive emotions? Or would we specifically look to leverage colors that elicit “paradoxical emotions”. With in the work we look at the research findings from two studies. The first study looks at establishing color as a language where there are consistent color association links. The second study builds on the findings that suggest of all the colors, Red has strong positive and negative association. Thus the second inquiry was motivated by the proposition that not all Reds stimulate the same emotional response. Thus to understand Red and its ability to be leveraged, we need to better understand if there are different Reds for positive or negative emotions, as well as individual emotions within these two segments.

1. Introduction

What if Red had multiple meanings? And what if its various meanings were opposing and contradicting to one another? Furthermore, what would it be like if colors were all correlated with both positive and negative associations and/or emotions? If this were the case, would we work with color differently and with greater caution when attempting to create desired user-experiences? Would we look to mitigate the negative emotions and support the positive emotions? Or would we specifically look to leverage colors that elicit “paradoxical emotions” (Desmet, 2004 p.12).

The question of whether or not design can produce unpleasant emotions is one of tremendous interest. In order to address this question one has to consider the ways in which emotions are ‘produced’ or ‘induced’ through the design of products and brands. One of design’s key premises is that it can create emotional user-experiences (Hekkert, 2001; Hummels, 1999; Overbeeke, Djajadiningrat, Wensveen, & Hummels, 1999) and thus engage the user in a desired way. Still, experience by nature is emergent rather than designed, and thus designing for desired experience can be a risky proposition. This risk factor is especially significant in cases where negative emotions, unplanned by the initial design, arise to dominate the experience.

Through our research on workplace design¹ we encountered examples where ‘good design intentions’ have led to discomfort, disappointment and/or the experience of negative emotions. All of these emotions were unplanned and yet strongly present. For example, in one of the new workspaces we studied, glass partitions were used extensively to allow for greater transparency so as to fit well with the nature of that business and its daily management needs. The design also led to an individual ‘no-privacy experience’ and as such it elicited a sense of resentment and discomfort towards this ‘over-exposure’. In another workspace design example, the excessive use of white in the space fit the design intention in that it was serene, but it also created a sense of alienation and detachment that was uninviting and a far cry from the sense of engagement and excitement the space had been designed to elicit².

¹ This research paper was submitted to the Space and Environment conference theme

² More details regarding this case can be found in our upcoming California Management Review article on Change management through workplace design.

As complexity theory (Stacey, 1996) advises us, reality of any kind has emergent qualities, which can not be forced. One can only design the 'container' in which reality evolves in the hope of inducing a desired result. Thinking through the characteristics of such a 'container' is a key tenet of complexity theory. Our research continually looks to address color-meaning within the context of color usage as a design lever. We view color as a design lever that can strongly influence and shape the 'container' in which certain user-experiences can later emerge. As such, we treat it as a significant design aspect that requires deep understanding.

Incorporating color into any design is a fundamental decision and is necessary at every level of the design. Smith (2003), studied designers' processes for making color decisions and found that they are often subjective and biased by personal experience and preferences, as well as by conventional knowledge and perception of particular colors. As in our Workplace Design Study as mentioned above, we found ample evidence that supported this practice. The architects interviewed for the study all attested to color selection based on individual biases and were often unable to explain why one color had been selected over another. In addition, in our discussions with architects and designers, they often acknowledged that there is little knowledge or support to draw upon for understanding how color decisions might be made differently or more effectively. Interestingly, our color-language research enabled us to look at color decisions from a different angle and consider their appropriateness to 'shaping the container'.

2. Color as Language

Our color-language proposition was motivated by the assumption that people consistently associate colors with certain meanings. The Merriam-Webster Online Dictionary defines language as a systematic means of communicating ideas or feelings by the use of conventionalized signs, sounds, gestures, or marks having understood meanings, or the suggestion by objects, actions, or conditions of associated ideas or feelings (*Merriam-Webster's collegiate dictionary*, 10th ed.,1993). Along the same lines, Crystal (1997) holds that the common purposes of language include: emotional expression, social interaction, recording of

facts, shaping reality, providing an instrument of thought, and expression of identity. We recruited these definitions to construct the argument of color as a language.

2a. Color Language Study Methodology

The sample used in this study included gender-balanced color professional and non-professional respondents (n = 177) representative of the US population between the ages of 18 - 55. All subjects were pre-tested for color blindness to determine their qualification to participate in the study. Participants answered a close-ended questionnaire that asked them to associate a pre-determined set of emotions and colors. To maintain homogeneity, a common color palette was used as a reference point (Figure 1) for all questions. The palette consisted of 10 colors in total, 7 hues: red, orange, yellow, green, blue, purple and brown. These colors were selected because they are consistent with colors used in other empirical studies on color associations. The three neutral colors of white, black, and gray were added to expand the palette to 10 colors and provide a point of comparison between chromatic and achromatic colors. Respondents were asked to refer to these colors when responding to each question.

Figure 1: Color Palette Employed

Plutchik (2003) was also among the firsts to introduce the concept of primary emotions as a categorizing method similar to that of primary colors in physics, where the combination of three primary colors can produce an infinite number of colors. Along this line any and all emotions that have ever been experienced can be produced by the combination of only the few primary emotions produced by the brain. An equally popular and important distinction is made between positive and negative emotions (Weiss & Cropanzano, 1996). Negative emotions include; fear, anxiety, anger, sadness, grief, rage, terror, disgust, remorse, pensiveness, boredom, disapproval and aggression to name some. Positive emotions on the other hand include joy, trust, admiration, vigilance, surprise, love, awe, optimism, serenity and acceptance. Although the listing of positive and negative emotions varies from one research to the other, overall there is an implicit agreement regarding the categorization method. The emotion typology used in this study was constructed from various existing typologies discussed above. (Table 1).

Table 1: Emotion Typology based on accumulation of existing emotion conceptualizations.

	Positive Emotions		
Secondary Emotions	Optimism Anticipation Awe	Joy Ecstasy Love Amazement Admiration Trust Surprise Interest Vigilance	Primary Emotions
	Pensiveness Boredom Distraction Apprehension Remorse Submission Annoyance Disapproval Contempt	Sadness Grief Disgust Anger Fear Loathing Rage Terror	
	Negative Emotions		

2b. Color Language Study Findings

Results from the study confirmed our proposition of color as an emotional language. There was a consistency of emotion association per color. Overall, people ascribe emotional associations to Red that are different from those assigned to Blue. This was consistent across a statistically significant body of respondents. We found significant associations between neutral hues used in this inquiry and negative emotions such as grief and boredom (Figure 2).

Figure 2: Findings of Color-Emotion associations

For the most part chromatic colors were associated with positive emotions while achromatic colors were associated with negative emotions. Conversely, chromatic colors were not associated with negative emotions, while achromatic colors were not associated with positive colors, with the exception of white (Figure 3).

Figure 3: Findings of Color-Emotion not association

Our research provides preliminary support to the existence of color language and also points to the consistent association of particular colors with negative emotions. Is it possible that the use of such colors in designed artifacts will elicit unpleasant emotions? Red is a color that our research shows holds a stake in both the positive and negative territories (figure 4). Is it then possible that the use of Red will trigger rage instead of love (the second strong emotional association to Red)?

Figure 4: Differences in Color-Emotion association between 'Colors' and 'Neutrals'

As we shape containers to evoke desired user-experiences, we need to be knowledgeable and conscious of color and meaning associations. The lack of consideration of color as a language that carries both positive and negative meanings might trigger those uninvited negative or unpleasant emotions. What remains to be answered is if contradicting meanings should exist, how can we mitigate them? If at all!

3. Red – A color with contradicting meaning

Red is perhaps the most investigated color of all, with most studies always including Red as one of the primary colors. It should be noted that many of these studies are void of context and look to understand colors on their own merits, before looking for context. Commonly held truths about this color from the kindergarten class (Boyatzis & Varghese, 1994) to the corporate boardroom (Dove, 1992) include associated meanings with love, anger, passion and war (Hupka, Zaleski, Otto, Reidl, & Tarabrina, 1997). Historically, we have associated Red with blood and thus it has universally been linked to the notion of life (Birren, 1950). From this association we have all come to believe that the heart is also Red and hence it is linked with love, Red is actually much more complex. Red is also the color of fire. We can see how the contradictory meanings can start to emerge from love to danger to desire. Red is a strong color that conjures up a range of seemingly conflicting emotions from passionate love to violence and warfare. Red is Cupid and the Devil.

Red is a very emotionally intense color. It enhances human metabolism, increases respiration rate, and raises blood pressure (Birren, 1978; Jacobs & Suess, 1975; Wilson, 1966). Red demands attention from the observer, and thus brings text and images to the foreground. Red is often used to evoke erotic feelings: Red lips, Red nails, and Red-light districts. At the same time it is used to elicit emotions of love: Red hearts, Red ribbons, Red roses. These notions are in support of our Color Language Study in which respondents segmented nine emotions for the original group of 27, which included both love and ecstasy.

In language, Red has long been used in contradictory ways. A “Red-letter day” is one of special importance and good fortune. To “paint the town Red” is to celebrate. The “Red carpet

treatment” or “rolling out the Red carpet” is designed to make someone feel special. Yet to “see Red” is to be angry, and a “Red herring” is an irritating distraction. If a business is “in the Red,” it is losing money, and thus Red is a color financial institutions traditionally stay away from, if only just to not tempt fate.

While much of this might seem like folklore rather than scientifically based knowledge, there is support for many of these statements. Jacobs and Suess (1975) found that Red had significantly higher anxiety-state scores compared to blue and green. Red was also found to be more arousing (Gerard, 1959; Goldstein, 1942). Wexner’s (1954) research sought to link words to describe moods to colors, and revealed in particular that Red was found to be most often associated with excitement and stimulation. The work of Osgood, Suci & Tannenbaum (1957) is of particular interest as their semantic differential technique looks specifically at the factor of evaluation which is defined as positive to negative. The other two factors in their work include activity as passive to active and potency as weak to strong. Red’s link to life (Fehrman & Fehrman, 2004), primarily thorough its association with blood, has made it one of the most significant colors in every culture (Fehrman & Fehrman, 2004). Because of this early association with blood it is suggested that “Red is charged with passionate emotion” such as love, courage, lust, murder, rage and joy, showing its full range from positive to negative associations (p.66).

But do we really know this to be true? Looking deeper into what we hold to be truths, there seems to be little hard evidence. Yet when one ventures to question friends and colleagues about color associations, in all likelihood, they will all be able to recite many of the above attributes for Red.

Thus we looked to build on our original color-language research to further understand the only color from our study and literature that holds such strong contradictory meaning.

4. Research description and results for Red Study

4a. Proposition:

This inquiry was motivated by the proposition that not all Reds stimulate the same emotional response. Thus to understand Red and its ability to be leveraged, we need to better understand if

there are different Reds for positive or negative emotions, as well as individual emotions within these two segments. The study does not look at this time to understand the significance if any of the context the color is used.

4b. Background:

Red is a color that has a rich and long history, one that can be linked to human existence. Many brands and products look to leverage Red as part of their communication efforts with customers, based on the assumption that it has the power to either stimulate or evoke specific physical and emotional responses. However, there are no studies that actually look to further segment our knowledge of Red. Is one Red a symbol of love and not anger? Is the same Red capable of being both passion and love or fear and anger? Without this information how can designers truly leverage Red as they desire to? Without this knowledge do designers risk sending conflicting messages, or worse, enlisting rage when passion is desired?

4c. Study design:

Building on the work on Color Language (Lechner & Harrington, 2003), we sought to increase our understand of the nine emotions identified to be linked with Red. From these identified emotions: aggression, amazement, anger, ecstasy, joy, love, passion, rage, and terror, participants were asked to identify which color each emotion represented from a palette of 25 different colors of Red (Figure 1). Since there was limited theory to guide the color selection, we were faced with developing a framework that we assumed would support the colors participants would desire without guiding or other influencing. The Reds selected for the study encompassed values ranging from light to dark and hue shifts, with the center row being closest to pure Red and moving more towards yellow-reds on the left and blue-reds on the right. This allowed for participants to indicate both the lightness and hue of the color that best aligned with the emotion.

Figure 5: Red Color Framework

The sample consisted of 186 participants. Three versions of printed ink on paper instrument were randomly distributed between participants who were assembled together in a conference room. Instrument one used all nine positive and negative emotions $n=57$ (figure 2), instrument two used only positive emotions $n=68$ (figure 3), and instrument three used only negative emotions $n=61$ (figure 4). The three instruments were employed to additionally determine if a difference would emerge on color-emotion links based on the set of emotions a participant had to handle.

Study of Red

INSTRUCTIONS - Link each of the emotions listed below, with the color that you feel best represents that emotion, by **writing the number** for each emotion in the colored square you selected. More than one emotion can be assigned to the same color.

Emotion List

1. Terror
2. Passion
3. Anger
4. Love
5. Rage
6. Ecstasy
7. Joy
8. Amazement
9. Aggression

Please complete

Gender	Age	Ethnicity
<input type="checkbox"/> Male	<input type="checkbox"/> Under 20	<input type="checkbox"/> African American
<input type="checkbox"/> Female	<input type="checkbox"/> 20-29	<input type="checkbox"/> Caucasian
	<input type="checkbox"/> 30-39	<input type="checkbox"/> Hispanic
	<input type="checkbox"/> 40-49	<input type="checkbox"/> Asian
	<input type="checkbox"/> 50-59	<input type="checkbox"/> Other
	<input type="checkbox"/> 60+	

E-mail: _____

Optional - Please supply your e-mail should you like to receive a copy of the study results.

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Figure 6: Positive and Negative Emotion Instrument

Study of Red

Directions - Link each of the emotions listed below, with the color that you feel best represents that emotion, by **writing the number** for each emotion in the colored square you selected. More than one emotion can be assigned to the same color.

Emotion List

1. Passion
2. Love
3. Ecstasy
4. Joy
5. Amazement

Please complete

Gender	Age	Ethnicity
<input type="checkbox"/> Male	<input type="checkbox"/> Under 20	<input type="checkbox"/> African American
<input type="checkbox"/> Female	<input type="checkbox"/> 20-29	<input type="checkbox"/> Caucasian
	<input type="checkbox"/> 30-39	<input type="checkbox"/> Hispanic
	<input type="checkbox"/> 40-49	<input type="checkbox"/> Asian
	<input type="checkbox"/> 50-59	<input type="checkbox"/> Other
	<input type="checkbox"/> 60+	

E-mail: _____

Optional - Please supply your e-mail should you like to receive a copy of the study results.

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Figure 6: Positive Emotion Instrument

Study of Red

Directions - Link each of the emotions listed below, with the color that you feel best represents that emotion, by **writing the number** for each emotion in the colored square you selected. More than one emotion can be assigned to the same color.

Emotion List

1. Terror
2. Anger
3. Rage
4. Aggression

Please complete

Gender	Age	Ethnicity
<input type="checkbox"/> Male	<input type="checkbox"/> Under 20	<input type="checkbox"/> African American
<input type="checkbox"/> Female	<input type="checkbox"/> 20-29	<input type="checkbox"/> Caucasian
	<input type="checkbox"/> 30-39	<input type="checkbox"/> Hispanic
	<input type="checkbox"/> 40-49	<input type="checkbox"/> Asian
	<input type="checkbox"/> 50-59	<input type="checkbox"/> Other
	<input type="checkbox"/> 60+	

E-mail: _____

Optional - Please supply your e-mail should you like to receive a copy of the study results.

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Figure 7: Negative Emotion Instrument

4d. Data collection:

Data was collected using a printed color on paper instrument that was completed by all participants at the beginning of either of the two seminar sessions. Instruments were randomly distributed onto the chairs of the conference room, and participants were asked to complete the form while waiting for the session to begin. Because it was not mandatory, not all session attendees completed the form. While it is recognized that lighting is an important variable in color testing and evaluation, the room lighting was constant for all participants. By having three different instruments, there was less likeliness that neighboring participants would copy from each other or be otherwise influenced. It is acknowledged that printed color has less control than using color standards and system colors that would control for stepping between value and hue shifts.

4e. Findings:

Overall, all four negative emotions: aggression, anger, rage, and terror, were viewed as similar, being generally on the yellow side and darker than the central red hue. Of the five positive emotions: amazement, ecstasy, joy, love and passion, the range was slightly or moderately on the blue side and mid to lighter than the central red hue. Thus there was a clear separation in perception. Furthermore there was little evidence of a difference between the average ratings of participants who completed the instruments with only one type of emotion versus those who completed the instruments with both positive and negative emotions.

4f. Conclusions:

There is support for the notion that the value and the hue of a Red *is* different for emotions that are positive versus negative. While we are not able to specify exactly which colors are linked to which emotions, we can suggest that colors that are in the lower left quadrant of our Red framework tend to be viewed more negatively, while colors in the top right quadrant are viewed more positively (figure 5). There was also no significant difference found along the lines of gender or age. In addition, the lack of difference between the three groups indicates that these color-emotion associations hold true regardless of the emotion set one works with.

This research program was intended as investigative, and thus future research is needed to further support or refute and refine findings. Additional research that seeks to specifically identify color/per each emotion should consider using a standardized color system to allow for generalization, control of color hue, and value steps. In addition, this study worked with a small set of identified emotions. The implicit assumption employed, that other emotions are not connected to Red in some way, should be examined, as we believe that individuals might be capable of assigning a specific Red for a much larger emotional set.

Figure 8: Red Positive & Negative Emotion Space

5. Conclusions and Future Direction:

This work supports the notion that Red does indeed have multiple meanings that encompass both positive and negative emotions, and that these various meanings are opposing and contradicting to one another. Building on the notion that “when experiencing products, people’s emotions are triggered through the senses” (Givechi, 2004 p.43), color becomes a critical design lever. As

such, it seems that designers need to carefully select the colors they use because negative emotions can be triggered as easily as positive ones can be. Designers should also be aware of the opportunity to leverage paradoxical emotions as a way to create “products that are unique, innovative, rich and more challenging or appealing than those that elicit only pleasant emotions” (Desmet, 2004 p.12).

Of course this investigation is still in its infancy and there are many unanswered questions, some of which include:

1. Does this notion of positive and negative emotion space for a specific color pertain to all colors or only individual colors?
2. Building off the study of the nine emotions studied, is it possible to single out a specific Red that can be linked to each emotion?
3. Do other unstudied positive and negative emotions identified within our typology also align themselves within this framework?
4. Can the contradictory nature of some colors allow designers to leverage them in designing for paradoxical emotions?

In addition there is also the notion of context. This research looked at color as an abstract concept. There still remains the question of if and/or how these findings would be impacted by varied design contexts. To date much research on color and emotions is void of context, and thus this is an area that offers much future research potential.

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